

THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Annotation: Abdulla Avloni, who was concerned about the future of the nation, while thinking about child education, divided the education process into three parts: "Body education", "Thought education" and "Ethical education". After all, it is not for nothing that A. Avloni put "Body - education" in the first place. "Healthy and strong body is the most necessary thing for a person. Because in order to study, learn and teach, a person needs a strong, disease-free body. People who do not have a healthy body cannot do many good things. A strong and healthy body is necessary for the education of thought," he said for no reason. The article describes the importance of physical education in the formation of a healthy lifestyle.

Key words: Body - education, healthy lifestyle, physical education, physical activity, active games, physical training.

INTRODUCTION

Health cannot be bought with all the material wealth and money. A person can live happily only when he has good health. Therefore, health should be valued as the highest among all existing values. For this, everyone should know the way to good health, the secrets of health, and realize that the only way to full health is a healthy lifestyle.

Today, the role of a healthy lifestyle in human life is very important. A healthy lifestyle helps a person in all spheres of activity and his actions. Due to

this approach to the human body, a person does not face various problems with himself, and instead embodies a high intellectual ability and a good mood during the day. It occupies an important place among people in our society. Nowadays, in a developed society, maintaining the health of the population should be one of the priority tasks in every country. This is important for the development of the state not only in the field of sports, but also in the social, economic, scientific and technical fields.

It is known that a healthy lifestyle is a lifestyle that does not contain harmful factors affecting people's health, and a person should consciously avoid them. The main directions of a healthy lifestyle:

- Follow the rules of personal hygiene;
- physical activity;
- compliance with the agenda;
- abstaining from harmful habits;
- proper nutrition;
- mental peace;
- medical culture;
- sex education.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

It is known that lifestyle can be healthy and unhealthy. People who lead a healthy lifestyle organize their daily life correctly. It is important to note that reading, sleeping, walking, eating, resting, laughing, coughing are specific norms, and the violation of this norm in a certain sense harms health.

The most common factors affecting healthy lifestyle are tobacco products and alcohol consumption. They harm not only the addict, but also their partners.

It is especially dangerous to smoke tobacco products, because the body of tobacco smokers is poisoned with harmful substances. For example: All internal organisms are damaged, hair, nails, skin color deteriorates.

The appearance of a person becomes ugly. During pregnancy, not only the child, but also the whole body is affected by pathology. The human immune system weakens.

Cardiovascular and nervous system deteriorates and brain activity is disturbed. Therefore, it is appropriate for the body to rest, eat at the right time, and regularly engage in sports at the right time. The role and importance of physical education in the human body consists in strengthening human health through the improvement of all body systems. The place and importance of physical education is an example of the fact that human development is a huge pedagogical process aimed at achieving maximum aspects. Playing with various new combinations and physical exercises learns how to express one's feelings. This helps to develop one's creative abilities. When performing various complex physical tasks, one's self-confidence increases when the exercises are successfully performed. a feeling of respect for the surrounding people also appears. At the same time, a person tries to overcome fear and shyness. In this case, various additional exercises help to form a healthy lifestyle. Therefore, physical education plays an important role in the development of a child.

Protection of the environment and its rational use is also an important resource for human life. Low sunlight and high temperature water or air temperature and high humidity are examples of this. If the environment is cleaned by people, the environment itself becomes important for people to walk fresh and live a healthy life during the day. Natural and anthropogenic factors play a major role in environmental pollution. Based on natural factors, environmental pollution occurs naturally as a result of lightning, wildfires, forest fires, volcanic eruptions, wind and other processes. Currently, artificial factors are most involved in plant pollution. It accounts for 2/3 of the pollution released into the atmosphere. Natural resources natural resources are used in the economy to meet the material and spiritual needs of society and are necessary for the living and survival of mankind,

the natural components of the surrounding natural environment are sources of energy. In short, if the environment is clean and healthy, the person himself and the people around him live enjoying the nature of the environment.

An inseparable component of education is physical education," said Abu Ali ibn Sina. From time immemorial, our people have paid great attention, respect and envy to physically strong and mentally healthy people. One such person, Pahlavon Mahmud, the original son of the Khorezm nation, a wrestler who never touched the ground, was recognized as a national hero. Today, our compatriots who are showing the sport of our independent country to the world are increasing day by day. In order to develop sports, Decrees and decisions created a great ground for the development of physical education and sports in our country, and at the same time, for the formation of a healthy generation. The organization of "Umid Nihollar" games among schoolchildren, "Barkamol Avlod" among college and high school students, and "Universiade" among university students is the basis for the popularization of physical culture and sports in our country. Before each young person chooses a type of physical education, first of all, he should evaluate his health level by passing a medical examination, which type of sport can be practiced, depending on his age, the season, and the current state of the body. It is necessary to choose the right type of physical activity, assessing the condition and similar characteristics. Instilling love for physical education and sports in every person starts from the family. Abu Ali ibn Sina wrote: "A person who regularly does physical exercises rarely needs treatment." 8 Health and educational tasks of physical education are as follows: - you will be in a good mood throughout the day; - your work will be productive, your creative activity will be strong; - the nervous system will be balanced, you will be calm and thoughtful; - forms the feelings of activity, initiative, difficulty, bravery, friendship; - regular exercise leads to the formation of hygienic skills; - fats in the body will decrease, you will be compact, dexterous, agile; - your muscles will tighten, your figure will be

beautiful and handsome; - the flow of blood in the veins is improved, the flow of oxygen and nutrients to the body and organs is improved; - the body's protective ability increases; - you will be younger, handsome, hardworking and healthy than others. Among the methods of physical health, morning physical education is important because of its popularity.

Morning physical education wakes up the body, improves metabolism, gives pleasure and activity to the body, improves mood, helps to get rid of numbness. Morning physical education, if done every day at the right time in the open air, not only has a good effect, but also increases the depth and ability to study throughout the day. Due to human laziness, most of our young people spend their valuable time in front of the TV, computer, watching various shows, playing games, drinking beer and other drinks instead of engaging in physical activities that are useful for them. they prefer to spend it "resting" by drinking. As a result, they suffer from various diseases due to such low mobility. No matter what the movements are, they are related to energy consumption due to the active work of the body and organs. Types of actions necessary for everyone's daily life: - work; - sports games; - dance; - yoga exercises; - physical education (physical culture), etc. Today's youth are the people who will realize the development of our country and our goals tomorrow. They must be mature in all aspects, including physically healthy. Abdulla Avloni, who was concerned about the future of the nation, while thinking about child education, divided the education process into three parts: "Body education", "Thought education" and "Ethical education". After all, it is not for nothing that A. Avloni put "Body - education" in the first place. "Healthy and strong body is the most necessary thing for a person. Because in order to study, learn and teach, a person needs a strong, disease-free body. People who do not have a healthy body cannot do many good things. A strong and healthy body is necessary for the education of thought," he said for no reason.

CONCLUSION

The role and importance of physical activity in organizing a healthy lifestyle throughout our life is very great. It is important for every person to have personal hygiene, nutrition, the importance of physical education and the protection of the environment. keeps well, improves blood circulation in the human body. will bring. Especially if our women are engaged in sports, "healthy pheasant from a healthy mother" will be born, and the young people of our future will achieve great goals. Because the prosperity, prosperity and development of our country is in the hands of this young generation. A country with healthy children will be powerful.

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